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Abstract

Environmental pollutants, particularly persistent organic pollutants but also widespread short-lived ones (bisphenol family and phthalates), also may be endocrine disruptors. These molecules are emerging in the etiology of the world-wide epidemic of chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes and the metabolic syndrome. These pollutants mainly bind either xenosensors or endocrine receptors, which then act as transcription factors. On the one hand, recent epidemiological studies have pinpointed the association between human exposure to mixtures of such contaminants and metabolic disorders. On the other hand, numerous studies in animal and in vitro models have described the consequences of exposure to individual pollutants in terms of modifications of the transcriptome or the metabolome implicating diverse signaling and metabolic pathways linked to obesity or the metabolic syndrome. The objectives of this commentary are 1) to give an overview of the potential role of organic pollutant mixtures on metabolic dysfunction, with a focus on obesity, type 2 diabetes and the metabolic syndrome in humans, as assessed by epidemiological studies; 2) to assess the state of art of in vitro and in vivo models to address this question, since most studies focus on the effects of single pollutants and 3) to evaluate the limits of the various models, in relation to the epidemiological studies.

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Role of mixtures of organic pollutants in the development of metabolic disorders *via* the activation of xenosensors.

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short : Xenosensors of organic pollutant mixtures and metabolic dysfunctions

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Abstract

Environmental pollutants, particularly persistent organic pollutants but also widespread short-lived ones (bisphenol family and phthalates), also may be endocrine disruptors. These molecules are emerging in the etiology of the world-wide epidemic of chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes and the metabolic syndrome. These pollutants mainly bind either xenosensors or endocrine receptors, which then act as transcription factors. On the one hand, recent epidemiological studies have pinpointed the association between human exposure to mixtures of such contaminants and metabolic disorders. On the other hand, numerous studies in animal and *in vitro* models have described the consequences of exposure to individual pollutants in terms of modifications of the transcriptome or the metabolome implicating diverse signaling and metabolic pathways linked to obesity or the metabolic syndrome. The objectives of this commentary are 1) to give an overview of the potential role of organic pollutant mixtures on metabolic dysfunction, with a focus on obesity, type 2 diabetes and the metabolic syndrome in humans, as assessed by epidemiological studies; 2) to assess the state of art of *in vitro* and *in vivo* models to address this question, since most studies focus on the effects of single pollutants and 3) to evaluate the limits of the various models, in relation to the epidemiological studies.

Bullets (highlights):

Chemical compounds, either natural or produced for industrial purposes, increasingly appear to be environmental pollutants and endocrine disrupters.

Epidemiological studies, worldwide, have shown associations between exposure to one or a family of pollutants and increased incidences of metabolic disruptions.

Animal and *in vitro* models provide direct evidence that links exposure to pollutants with metabolic disruption phenotypes.

Even though evidence is converging, the experimental models have limits and data are still missing to draw firm conclusions, especially on the effects of mixtures.

1. Introduction

Living organisms are exposed to various xenobiotics (xeno: foreign, biotics: living). During the course of time, they have been and continue to be produced naturally, for example by fires and volcanoes. During the course of human evolution and, especially, during the last two centuries with the occurrence of the industrial revolution, there has been an exponential increase in the number of chemical compounds, some of which are toxic. Among them are the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and the endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs). POPs are defined by the Stockholm Convention as compounds that have a slow rate of biodegradation, long distance transportation, high lipophilicity and, thus, bioaccumulation in fat tissues. Although most POPs have been banned, their study is still of interest for understanding their effects on health. EDCs are defined as interfering with any aspect of hormonal action [1]. Some molecules are both POPs and EDCs and, therefore, may disrupt cell physiology.

The WHO has declared obesity (defined as $BMI \geq 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$ for adults by the WHO, and for children as a weight-for-height greater than 3 (age < 5 years) or 2 (age > 5 years) standard deviations above the WHO Child Growth Standards or Reference median) and its related diseases, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, musculoskeletal disorders and some cancers, as a worldwide epidemic burden [2]. Xenobiotics, especially EDCs, have multiple deleterious effects, among which carcinogenicity and alterations of the reproductive system have been the most studied ([3] for a review). Many epidemiological studies now have reported associations between the levels of various contaminants, mainly POPs, and metabolic disorders. Thus, an increasing number of studies now focus on metabolic disruption by pollutants. For example, Toxicant-Associated Fatty Liver Disease (TAFLD) has been described as a form of NAFLD (Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease) associated with exposure to industrial chemicals, such as vinyl chloride in workers [4] or various polychlorobiphenyls (PCBs) and heavy metals in the NHANES cohort [5]. The liver, one of the main metabolic regulators, participates in the control of the levels of blood glucose, lipids, amino acids, lactate and ammonia. Other tissues also regulate metabolism: adipose tissue (triglyceride storage, adipokine secretion), the pancreas (hormone release), smooth muscle (glycogen storage) and the kidney (blood filtration). We will focus, mainly, on the metabolic syndrome (hypertension, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia) which is often linked to obesity and type 2 diabetes and which has been associated with exposure to organic pollutants, alone or in combination.

Humans (as well as entire ecosystems) were and still are increasingly exposed to POPs. The rapidity with which these molecules have appeared has not permitted living organisms to modify their arsenal of proteins to combat potentially toxic effects. At present, three proteins, called xenosensors, are known to respond to xenobiotics which an organism might encounter: the Aryl Hydrocarbon Receptor (AHR), the Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) and the Constitutive Androstane Receptor (CAR) (Table 1). These

intracellular receptors bind the xenobiotics and transactivate the expression of target genes, mainly xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes. These enzymes modify the molecules to permit their elimination from the body and allow the survival of the cells. In addition to exogenous ligands, endogenous ligands, such as tryptophan derivatives, also bind the xenosensors, as described recently for the aryl hydrocarbon receptor [6]. Moreover, endocrine receptors and other nuclear receptors can bind some pollutants. Presumably, endocrine receptors were not initially destined to perform such an activity and cellular dysfunctions result. Today, about 15 receptors, which can bind various xenobiotics, have been described (Table 1).

Given the number of xenobiotics (more than 100,000 referenced chemicals), the possible combinations, which represent the exposure of a human organism from conception throughout its life (defined as the exposome by C. Wild [7]), are vast. Since current research technologies are incapable of testing all the possible combinations of compounds, alternate approaches need to be employed. Two complementary approaches that have been developed are: i) the study of the effects of authentic exposures as determined by measurements from blood, urine or hair samples from cohorts or known mixtures (mixtures of polychlorobiphenyls (PCBs) such as Arochlor®, ClophenA60® or Phenoclor® sold by several companies [8]) and ii) the study of intracellular signaling pathways that are dysregulated following the activation of one or several xenosensors by prototypical ligands in *in vivo* and *in vitro* models. However, cross-talks between several receptors or their pathways, such as the interaction between the AHR and ER α [9], have been documented which may complicate interpretation of the experimental results. A role via the binding to xenosensors of many contaminants is now well documented in *in vitro* cellular models and in various animal species, especially rodents. However, extrapolation of the results obtained in these models to the potential effects found in human populations is not always direct, nor are correlations with epidemiological studies. The effects of complex mixtures, with an emphasis on low and chronic exposures, are now being investigated increasingly in *in vivo* and *in vitro* models.

Among all chemicals, those which belong to the POP/EDC families are a major concern, first because of their persistence and second because of their interaction with the endocrine system, which finely regulates the body weight and other metabolic functions. This commentary will discuss the effects of exposure to mixtures of pollutants on metabolic dysfunction in several models and in humans and will highlight the limits of these studies.

Table 1: List of receptors which bind xenobiotics. For each, examples of endogenous and exogenous ligands are given [10–15]. *considered as hormones by some authors (bile acids [16]; 9-*cis* RA [17]). For abbreviations of xenobiotics, see Table 2.

Acronyme	Approved Symbol (Nuclear Receptor family)	Receptor name	Example(s) of xenobiotics	Example of endogenous ligand(s)
Xenobiotic receptors (xenosensors)				
AHR	AHR	Aryl Hydrocarbon Receptor	Dioxins, DPCBs	Indol and tryptophan derivatives
PXR (=SXR)	NR1I2	Pregnane-X-Receptor	NPCBs (PCB-153), several drugs	5 β -cholestane-3 α 7 α ,12 α -triol, steroids, bile acids*
CAR	NR1I3	Constitutive Androstane Receptor	NPCBs (PCB-153), several drugs	Androstane and derivatives
Endocrine nuclear receptors				
ER α , β	ESR1 (NR3A1), ESR2 (NR3A2)	Estrogen Receptor	Bisphenol A (BPA), pesticides (DDT)	β -17-estradiol
AR	AR (NR3C4)	Androgen Receptor	<i>p,p'</i> -DDE	Testosterone
PR	PGR (NR3C3)	Progesterone Receptor	Musk compounds	progesterone
TR α , β	THRA (NR1A1), THRB (NR1A2)	Thyroid hormone Receptor	Hydroxylated Polybrominated Diphenyl Ethers	Thyroid hormones
GR	NR3C1	Glucocorticoid Receptor	Tolyfluanid, DPCBs, PCB methyl sulphones	cortisol
VDR	NR1I1	Vitamin D Receptor	Curcumin	1,25-dihydroxy-vitamin D (calcitriol)
Other nuclear receptors				
PPAR α , δ , γ	PPARA (NR1C1), PPARD (NR1C2), PPARG (NR1C3)	Peroxisome Proliferator-activated Receptor	Phthalates, organotins	Arachidonic acid derivatives, linoleic acid derivatives
FXR	NR1H4	Farnesoid X Receptor	Pyrethroids	Bile acids*
RXR α , β , γ	RXRA (NR2B1), RXRB (NR2B2), RXRG (NR2B3)	Retinoid X Receptor	Organotins (tributyltin)	9- <i>cis</i> -retinoic acid*
RAR α , β , γ	RARA (NR1B1), RARB (NR1B2), RARG (NR1B3)	Retinoic Acid Receptor	Organochlorine pesticides, alkylphenols, phthalate esters	All <i>trans</i> retinoic acid
LXR α/β	LXRA (NR1H3), LXRB (NR1H2)	Liver X Receptor	PFOA	oxysterol

2. Pollutant – Metabolic Disruption Relationships

2.1. Epidemiological studies

The chemical obesogen hypothesis was introduced first by Grün and Blumberg in 2006 [18]. The fact that many pollutants can bind hormonal receptors involved in metabolism has been an incentive for more research. Since then, numerous epidemiological studies, worldwide, have shown associations between exposures to one or a family of pollutants and increased incidences of metabolic disruptions. However, few studies have dealt with mixtures of pollutants that belong to different chemical families or which act through different receptors. Below, we comment on a few selected studies. Information about the cohorts, POPs and metabolic disruption is summarized in Table 2.

Studies of the NHANES (1999-2006) American cohort have shown that exposures to PCBs, lead and mercury are associated with insulin resistance, metabolic syndrome [19,20] and unexplained alanine amino transferase elevations, a proxy marker of NAFLD [5]. Another meta-analysis also reported associations between type 2 diabetes and various POPs (organochlorine compounds, PCBs, and dioxins and dioxin-like chemicals)[21]. In Europe, the project OBELIX initiated in 2009, which uses mother-child cohorts from 4 European regions, aims to assess and characterize, in humans, the effects of early life exposure to major classes of EDCs (dioxin-like compounds, non-dioxin-like PCBs, organochlorine pesticides, brominated flame retardants, phthalates, and perfluorinated compounds) which have been identified as potential inducers of obesity [22]. Another European project, ENRIECO, combines eight cohorts with children recruited between 1985 and 2004 [23]. In these two last projects, a relationship between some of the pollutants investigated (PCB-153, *p,p'*-DDE, PFOA, PFOS) and metabolic disorders was found [24–27]. The INMA project combines 7 Spanish cohorts and is designed to study the impact of environmental exposures on children's health by following pregnant women and their children. With respect to metabolic disorders, the study shows that *p,p'*-DDE exposure of the mother is associated with rapid weight gain in the first months after birth and, subsequently, an elevated BMI [28]. Tobacco smoking (smoke contains several POPs) also has been associated with the metabolic syndrome in a meta-analysis of 13 cohorts [29].

At least, two limitations arise from the studies of cohorts: 1) the causality link between exposure to POPs and a pathology is difficult to ascertain; 2) few studies try to link a pathology to a signaling or molecular pathway (the study by Remy and colleagues [25] is one example of such an attempt). A recent review of the literature pinpointed the strengths and limitations of studies concerning the link between EDCs and diabetes or metabolic syndrome [3]. Therefore, studies employing *in vivo* and *in vitro* models are necessary.

Table 2: Characteristics of a selection of cohorts which link a mixture of pollutants to either diabetes or metabolic disorder endpoints.

Name of cohort/ number of individuals	Families (classes) and number of POPs measured	POPs related to diabetes	POPs related to other metabolic related endpoints	Reference
NHANES 1999-2002 / 1721 subset/ 179 diabetics	PCDDs, PCDFs, DPCBs, NPCBs, OC pesticides (19)	DPCBs, OC pesticides	DPCBs, OC pesticides: Insulin resistance	[19]
NHANES 1999-2002/ 721 non diabetic subset / 175 metabolic syndrome	PCDDs, PCDFs, DPCBs, NPCBs, OC pesticides, (19)	No diabetic patient included	DPCBs, NPCBs, OC pesticides : metabolic syndrome (3 or 4 components/5)	[20]
NHANES 2003-2004/ 4582 subset (after exclusion criteria defined in publication)	PFCs, As, Hg, PAH, heavy metals, OC pesticides, PBDEs, Phthalates, PCDDs, PCDFs, DPCBs, NPCBs, cotinine, OP, perchlorate, phenols, iodine	Not tested	Lead, blood mercury, PCBs (DPCBs + NPCBs): alanine aminotransferase elevation (representative of NAFLD)	[5]
Assessment of 72 epidemiological studies from 1997 to 2010 (National Toxicology Program)	Various POPs: trans-nonachlor, <i>p,p'</i> DDE, DDT, DDD, PCBs, TCDD/agent orange, OC compounds, brominated and perfluoroalkyl compounds	OC compounds, PCBs: Type 2 diabetes	Not tested	[21]
Uljin cohort: 246 subset / 64 metabolic syndrome	15 PCBs and 8 OC pesticides	Not tested	Metabolic syndrome defined by 3 criteria of NCEP ATP III modified	[30]
OBELIX project: HUMIS, FLEHS I and PCB birth cohorts. 2002-2009 or 2002-2004. 4937 subset / 367 (infant growth) or 251 (BMI)	Dioxin-like compounds (DR-CALUX bioassay for all cohorts) and dioxins, furans, non-ortho-PCBs and mono-ortho-PCBs in a subset of HUMIS	Not tested	Perinatal exposure to dioxins: increased growth for 2 year-old infants (borderline statistical significant association) and increased BMI (due to weight) for 7 year-old girls	[24]
OBELIX project: FLEHS II birth cohort 2007-2011 / 195 subset	Pb, Mn, Cu, Tl, As, Cd, PCB-153, <i>p,p'</i> DDE, HCB, PFOS, PFOA, Hg, Hg-MM, MECPP, MEHHP, MEOHP, PM 2.5	Not tested	Cord blood transcriptome analysis: TF and GR by PCB-153, <i>p,p'</i> DDE; TF and PGR by PFOS, PFOA. Insulin receptor, acute phase response, IL-6 and prolactin signaling by <i>p,p'</i> DDE	[25]
ENRIECO project: assessment of 12 birth cohorts studies 1990 to 2008	PCB-153, <i>p,p'</i> DDE,	Not tested	PCB-153 exposure: decreased birth weight	[26,27]
INMA project: 7 birth cohorts 2004-2006/ 518 infants	<i>p,p'</i> DDE, HCB, β HCH, PCB (118, 138, 153, 180)	Not tested	<i>p,p'</i> DDE exposure: rapid weight gain (first 6 months) and elevated BMI at 14 months for infants born from normal weight mothers	[28]
Assessment of 13 epidemiological studies / 56691 subjects / 8688 metabolic syndrome	Smoke (cigarette for 10 studies only)	Not tested	Active smoking related to metabolic syndrome in 9/13; no relation for 3 studies and 1 inverse relation. Metabolic syndrome defined by WHO guidelines or NCEP ATP III modified or not or ACE or AHA.	[29]

PCDD (polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxin), PCDF (polychlorinated dibenzofuran), PCBs, (polychlorinated biphenyl), DPCB (dioxin-like PCB), NPCB (non dioxin-like PCB), OC (organochlorine), OP (organophosphate insecticide), PBDE (polybrominated diphenyl ether), *p,p'*DDE (dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene), DDT (dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane), DDD (dichlorodiphenyl-dichloroethane), TCDD (2,3,7,8 tetrachlorodibenzo-*p*-dioxin) , HCB (hexachlorobenzene), PFOS (perfluorooctane sulfonate), PFOA (perfluorooctanoic acid), Hg-MM (methyl mercury), MECPP (mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate) , MEHHP (mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate), MEOHP (mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate), β HCH (beta-hexachlorocyclohexane), WHO (World Health Organization), NCEP ATP III (National Cholesterol Education Program's Adult Treatment Panel), ACE (American College of Endocrinology), AHA (American Heart Association).

2.2 *In vivo* and *in vitro* studies: from single to multiple exposures.

2.2.1 *In vivo* models

The relationship between exposure to pollutants and metabolic disruption was investigated first using single compounds and, mainly, animal models. The role of xenosensor signaling in metabolic disruption has been demonstrated in animal KO models. Experiments in rodents indicate that ligand-activated PXR regulates hepatic glucose and lipid metabolism which may, thus, affect whole body metabolic homeostasis (reviewed by [31]). Similarly, CAR is involved in overall energy metabolism, including hepatic glucose and cholesterol metabolism ([32] and reviewed in [33]). Finally, it has been suggested that AHR expression plays a role in the maintenance of lipid and glucose homeostasis in mice [34] and particularly with ageing [35]. The use of KO models have demonstrated that some endocrine receptors, for example the estrogen receptor α [36] or the more recently described GPER/GPR30, also are involved in glucose homeostasis (reviewed in [37]). Exposure to several environmental estrogen compounds (BPA, genistein, nonylphenol, ...) has been shown to activate GPER with potential endocrine disruption [38]. Moreover cross-talks between the receptors described in Table 1 (for example: ER α /AHR [9], ER β /PPAR γ [39], AHR/PPAR γ and for a review [40]) have been documented, thus enhancing the possible role of pollutants *via* the endocrine/xenosensor pathways and increasing the complexity of the regulations.

Associations between pollutants/xenobiotics and metabolic disorders also have been described with individual toxicants. For example, the exposure of mice to low doses (18 days, 5 to 500 ng/kg) of TCDD modifies the expression of hepatic genes involved in lipid and glucose metabolism in an AHR-dependent manner [41]. An exposure to low levels of this dioxin induces liver steatosis and fibrosis (6 weeks, 5 μ g/kg) [42] and obesity (32 weeks, 1 μ g/kg) [43] in mice receiving a high fat diet. Treatment of mice with BPA, PFOA or tributyltin also leads to diverse metabolic disorders [44–47].

Only a few studies in various models have focused on the effects of complex mixtures (which we define as compounds which belong to different chemical families or which affect different signaling pathways). For example, in relation to metabolic disorders, a mixture of 6 pesticides belonging to different families (alachlor, captan, diazinon, endosulfan, maneb, mancozeb) was shown to disturb glucose metabolism in female mice [48]. In another study, a mixture of 4 compounds (TCDD, PCD-153, Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, BPA) acting through different receptors triggered lipid metabolic disturbances in female mice [49].

2.2.2 *In vitro* models

Although metabolic disruptions are integrated pathologies which are difficult to study *in vitro*, human models are essential for deciphering molecular mechanisms. Numerous *in vitro* experiments have investigated how single xenobiotics activate xenosensors and endocrine disruptors. To extend knowledge about the effects of

chemicals on cellular functions, research programs such as ToxCast or Tox21, in the USA, have been initiated. These are based on high throughput, *in vitro* assays. Although certainly valuable, these studies evaluate mostly gene expression and provide little or no information about the obesogenic or diabetogenic-type activities of the chemicals.

However, studies of the effects of exposure of human cell lines or primary cultures to mixtures of pollutants are still rare. We investigated a mixture of TCDD and the organochlorine pesticide α -endosulfan in the human hepatic cell line HepaRG and showed that it disrupts the expression of genes involved in several metabolic pathways including glucose and lipid metabolism, in a more pronounced way than each pollutant alone [50]. In another human model, the adipose cell line hMADS, inflammation was shown to be the major pathway activated by a mixture of TCDD and PCBs [51]. Finally, in the human hepatic-derived HepG2 cell line, the combination of mixtures of brominated and perfluorinated pollutants was more potent than each individual mixture alone to produce reactive oxygen species with a possible link with the metabolic syndrome [52]. However, such studies still do not predict if co-exposures lead to additive, synergistic or antagonistic effects.

3. Limits of Models: “of mice and men” and women.

Although the ideal model is the human species, experimental approaches other than epidemiological studies clearly are not possible. As opposed to pharmacological studies, toxicologists obviously cannot test the effects of pollutants on humans. *In vitro* toxicological studies present two inconveniencies: 1) the large choice of models, even considering only 2D cell culture models and 2) the lack of a (few) good model(s) that adequately simulate human cellular metabolic responses (reviewed in [53]). Other models such as primary cultures, induced pluripotent stem cells, or tissue explants also have been employed but they too do not allow investigation of systemic effects. 3D cultures, co-cultures and organ-on-chip technology [54] are increasingly used for basic toxicological studies and may provide more “tissue-like” responses. 3D cell culture has been found to completely modify the cell phenotype (increased expression of albumin, urea, xenosensors and xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes in HepG2 cells [55]) which suggests that the interpretation of 2D cell culture results may need to be reconsidered.

Apart from bioethical considerations, toxicological studies on rodent models, even though still probably indispensable, face the inconvenience of inter-species variability. For example, studies that treat human and rodent primary hepatocytes with 2,3,7,8 tetrachlorodibenzo-*p*-dioxin (TCDD) produce non-identical lists of genes the expressions of which are altered [56,57]. Also, exposure to TCDD leads to severe liver toxicity in rodent models [58] whereas, in human populations exposed to TCDD, only mild liver symptoms, such as γ -glutamyltransferase elevation, have been described [59]. Also, scientists interested in models for NAFLD, which is highly correlated with obesity,

dyslipidemia and insulin resistance, have recently questioned the use of various rodent models to decipher human pathologies [60,61]. However, recent PXR and CAR gene KOs in the rat have been characterized and have been proposed as useful new tools for metabolic studies [62].

Finally, several studies have described sex-specific differences in energy metabolism with consequences for the metabolic syndrome, which suggests a role for sex hormones and their receptors in the response of the organisms to contaminant exposure and underscores the need for studies of both sexes (Le-Magueresse et al., 2017 in this issue [63]).

4. Pending Questions and Issues

There are still too few *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies which employ complex mixtures to strengthen the interpretation of results obtained in epidemiological studies of cohorts concerning the relationships between co-exposure to pollutants and metabolic disorders. Even fewer studies aim at the effect of mixtures of pollutants and drugs, although such combinations may activate receptors [64]. Increased coordination among studies *in vitro*, in animal models and in humans would allow a much stronger, more cohesive picture of the deleterious consequences of lifelong exposure to organic pollutants. This includes the development of more precise criteria, which are acceptable to the whole community of epidemiologists, for the sampling and conservation of biological matrices and for disease definition in a manner similar to the one now accepted for transcriptomics studies (MIAME). This is an important goal of major EU projects such as the HEALS project. This would require more concerted research approaches to design experiments and it should include systems biology. Indeed, a recent systems biology approach has revealed that pathways and targets activated by the combination of 3 POPs commonly detected in human tissues (*p,p'*-DDE, TCDD and PCB-153) are associated with type 2 diabetes [65].

Nevertheless, evidence concerning the link of metabolic disorders to exposure to individual organic pollutants is converging from *in vivo*, *in vitro* and epidemiological studies and it suggests that complex mixtures might have a more detrimental effect (as an example [66]). This calls for more studies about the possible underestimation of the potency of a pollutant in the case of co-exposure and also may have implications for the determination of TDIs (Tolerable Daily Intakes).

Obviously, given the subject and the focus on xenosensors, this paper can not be exhaustive regarding the link between xenobiotics, molecular and cellular mechanisms and metabolic disorders. We have not taken into account many studies which show that organic pollutants may modify epigenetic characteristics which are likely involved in these pathologies [67,68]. Recently, the microbiota has emerged as playing a role in the toxicity of pollutants [69,70]. Indeed, xenobiotics, such as benzo-a-pyrene, can modify the composition of the microbiota in humans [71]. Xenobiotics also can be metabolized

into new compounds which can activate xenosensors. For example, tryptophan is metabolized by the microbiota into AhR ligands [72]. Again, in these novel areas of investigation, most studies have used single pollutants.

While awaiting more definitive scientific results, a precautionary approach to risk management seems necessary for potential pollutants suspected of playing a role in pathologies which include the worldwide epidemic of obesity, diabetes and metabolic syndrome. This may include compounds identified by a “read-across” approach. Also, this should take into account the replacement of a pollutant with a known or suspected deleterious effect (such as bisphenol A) by a less studied molecule, such as its substitutes (bisphenol F or S) [67].

As was the case for the Uppsala consensus statement on environmental contaminants and the global obesity epidemic [73], which concluded that a « public health effort should focus on the prevention of early obesity prevention by means of reducing chemical exposures rather than only treating the established disease», there is a need for a similar consensus for metabolic disorders.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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* This article defines, for the first time, the exposome as « [a concept that] encompasses

life-course environmental exposures (including lifestyle factors), from the prenatal period onwards ». Determination of the exposome should identify factors that contribute to the development of pathologies independently of gene mutation. Thus, the exposome includes environmental exposures not only to xenobiotics but also to radiation and social stresses

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** This review focuses on the interactions in diverse models between environmental pollutants, which are known or suspected to be endocrine disrupters (bisphenol A, phthalates, brominated flame retardants...) and metabolic disorders.

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In vitro

- Modified expression of « metabolic » genes
- Xenosensor or endocrine receptor binding/activation
- Dysregulation of « metabolic » endpoints

In vivo

- metabolic disorder phenotype (steatosis, dyslipidemia, ...)

Epidemiology

- Mother/child transmission leading to higher sensitivity
- Obesity, diabetes, metabolic syndrome